

THE ROLE OF GEOMETRIC PROBLEMS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THINKING SKILLS OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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Abstract. *Arming the youth of today with the basics of science, achieving a high level of development of their mental thinking is one of the most important tasks facing the general education schools. In order to fulfill these tasks, primary school teachers become competitive specialists who will have their place in the society.*

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Arming the youth of today with the basics of science, achieving a high level of development of their mental thinking is one of the most important tasks facing the general education schools. In order to fulfill these tasks, primary school teachers become competitive specialists who will have their place in the society, increasing their role in the society, directing each lesson to teaching based on new innovative technologies is the demand of the time. Because a person living in this society is preparing for a wide range of activities, the introduction of advanced technologies into the educational process in the process of his development and renewal of thinking ensures the development of independent free thinking and creative activities of students. In the development of mental abilities of students in elementary grades, more attention should be paid to solving mathematical problems in mathematics. The role of teaching mathematical problems in elementary grades is great. Students who start solving problems acquire new mathematical knowledge and prepare for practical activities. Solving problems allows them to develop their logical thinking.

Mathematical problems are an important component of teaching mathematics. It is impossible to imagine mastering mathematics without solving problems. Solving mathematical problems is a natural way to put theory into practice. The child meets the problem from the first day of school activities. Solving problems is also very important in the personal education of students. In one of the first conversations with first-grade students, the teacher addresses the simplest question in order to determine what kind of life experience and knowledge the student has. Of course, the first issues that students will be familiar with should be understandable for students. It will be easier for students to understand the problems if the conditions of the content of the problems are vital and interesting. The process of working on issues is done consciously. They find the answer to the given question easily. For example: "You have 4 pencils, you got another one. How many pencils do you have?" Mathematical problems from the beginning to the end of teaching at school help students to correctly form mathematical concepts, to determine more deeply the various aspects of the interrelationship of the surrounding environment, to apply the studied theoretical rules, to various observed phenomena. allows you to set up a number of connections. At the same time, solving problems helps the development of the child's thinking.

A high level of development of mathematical thinking in elementary school students can be achieved only within the framework of properly organized school education. Philosophical understanding of the world, its general laws and basic scientific ideas is impossible without mathematics. Denying the existence of coincidences undermines our worldview. And that's why the science of chance is necessary to form a worldview in students. Another very important goal of mathematical education is to educate a person's ability to understand the content of the problem, to think correctly and logically, and to acquire algorithmic thinking skills. It is necessary for every student to be able to analyze, understand the content of the problem, to distinguish hypothesis from fact, to criticize, to clearly express his opinion and the like, and on the other hand, to develop imagination and intuition. Thus, mathematics is necessary for the mental development of an individual. The term "problem" is defined differently in different sources: Solving a problem means revealing the connection between the numbers given in the condition of the problem and the desired number, and choosing arithmetic operations on this basis, then performing them, and answering the question of the problem. Solving a problem means fulfilling the requirements of the problem through a logical sequence of actions on the numbers, quantities, and relationships that exist directly and indirectly in this problem. Problem solving develops thinking in children. "Thinking means an active reflection of the objective world in the human mind".

The work started in the first and second grades to develop the ability to solve simple and complex problems in the primary grade will be continued in the third grade. In the third grade, first of all, the skills and abilities to solve simple and complex problems introduced by the program in the courses of the first and second grades are further strengthened. When solving such problems, students perform appropriate calculations not only with one-digit, two-digit, and three-digit numbers, but also with multi-digit numbers. In addition, in the course of the third grade, a number of simple and complex problems of a new type are presented. In particular, in this course, simple problems related to motion, problems related to calculating the height, width and face of a rectangle, and problems related to calculating the time of the beginning of this event are given. Among complex problems, it is necessary to distinguish typical problems related to motion, proportionality, and finding the unknown by two differences. In the third grade, the main work is carried out for students to master the method of solving problems by creating equations. In particular, in the third grade, the ability to solve simple problems related to finding the unknown is strengthened. At the same time, children are first introduced to the algebraic method of solving simple problems related to the concepts of difference or ratio and various complex problems. Solving textual problems, in addition to developing one or another concept, relationship, calculation skills, allows to expand the scope of knowledge of students, to explain some quantities and the connections between them in depth. The extent to which students have mastered the general method of problem analysis and how they can use the tools that help them find a solution to the problem on their own plays an important role in the formation of problem-solving skills. Learning the content of the problem consists of making a short note of the problem, drawing up a solution plan, writing the solution with appropriate written or oral explanations, and checking the correctness of the solution. Working on the issue begins with mastering its content. Students should be able to clearly imagine the life situation reflected in it after reading the problem. Third graders should be able to do it independently. From the first grade, great attention is paid to the development of the ability to write a short essay. At the same time, in the first grade, the short writing of the problem was done mainly under the guidance of the teacher, and in the second and

third grades, the task of preparing the children to write the short writing of the problem independently is set. We remind you that when the condition of the problem is difficult, when it is difficult to understand the connections between the given ones, short writing is appropriate for solving new types of problems. Illustrating a number of problems with pictures and drawings is of great help, and it is impossible to give any general instructions for drawing or painting problems. Often, graphic images of the same issue can be presented in different ways. Therefore, the task of the teacher is to always lead this work, to help students in choosing the most rational forms of creating a graphic model. It is necessary to consider that it is not necessary to strictly adhere to the given plan when solving each issue. For example, if a familiar-looking problem is given and the student can imagine a way to solve it after reading it for the first time, strictly following the whole plan will be a reason to spend too much time. In this case, the student quickly solves the problem and checks the solution. Some students can solve one problem at once, other students can solve it by writing briefly, and so on. For example, if a teacher wants to find out how well children know how to write a short story, they can ask all the students to write a short story or draw a picture about the problem. Introducing how to work as a reminder to children can be done like this: - Today you will learn to work on the problem differently. We will solve the problems using the tasks written in the exhibitions in your hand. If you learn how to use exhibitions, you can solve the problem on your own. For example, "There were 40 buckets of water in the barrel. 12 buckets of water were taken in the morning and 15 buckets in the evening to water the flowers. How many buckets of water are left in the barrel?" - Kumri, read the first assignment. (The student reads the first task in the note) - Complete the task. (Everyone reads the problem inside.) - Steel, complete the second task (Reads) and write the condition.

There were 40 buckets.

Received - 12 and 15 buckets.

Left?

Matter. In the workshop, as many shirts and dresses are made, as many suits are sewn, 3 m for each shirt, 4 m for each suit, the material is spent. If 24 m of material was used for all dresses, how much material was used for all suits? A short version of the issue looks like this. Consumption rate for one garment

Number of garments	Total material consumption
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Dress and suit - 3 m and 4 m. For dresses - 24 m. Gone. The same 24 m - ?

Solving this problem is carried out by the method of creating problematic questions. As a result of the experiments and observations, general rules for activating the students' cognitive activities and using their intellectual capabilities at a high level during the educational process are developed. The desired issue consists of three components. a) the text of the problem, b) numerical facts in the problem and c) the question of the problem.

Before these three components, there are certain requirements.

1) The text of the issue: should be short, fluent and understandable.

2) Numerical facts: they should be selected logically and reveal the dynamic of our life and development.

3) At the end of the text there should be a clear question written in the form of an interrogative sentence.

In the process of solving problems, students acquire new mathematical knowledge and prepare for practical activities. Problems allow them to develop independent thinking. Also, problem solving is of great importance in the personal education of students. Therefore, it is

important for the teacher to have a deep understanding of the textual problem and its structure, to be able to solve such problems in different ways. A textual problem is an expression (description) of a situation (situations) in natural language, in which it is required to give a quantitative characteristic to some part of this situation, to determine whether there are some relations between its parts, or to determine the type of this relation.

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